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Research Article

Formulation And Development of Oral Fast Dissolving Tablets Using a Model Drug

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to develop fast dissolving tablets of cinnarizine by direct compression method. Micro crystalline cellulose (MCC) as diluent and super disintegrants, such as Croscopovidone (CP), Cinnarizine(drug), Magnesium Stearate, Talc, Mannitol and croscarmellose Sodium were used. Fast dissolving tablets disintegrates or dissolves rapidly within few seconds due to maximized pore structure in the formulation or by the action of superdisintegrants. Infrared (IR) spectroscopy was performed to identify the physicochemical interaction between drug and polymer. IR spectroscopy showed that there was no interaction of drug with polymer. Various pre-compression parameters such as angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, Hausner's ratio were carried out to study the flow properties of powder in order to achieve uniformity of tablet weight and the values were found within acceptable limits. The powder mixtures were compressed into tablet using punch tablet machine. The formulated tablets were evaluated for hardness, thickness, weight variation, friability % drug content, in vitro disintegration time in vitro drug release and all the values were found within permissible limits. The formulation F04 containing croscopovidone as superdisintegrant and MCC as diluent was found to be the optimized formulation on the basis of in vitro disintegration time and in vitro drug release. Stability studies were carried out at 40°C/ 75% RH for a period of 1 month for the selected formulations.

INTRODUCTION

The oral route of drug administration is the most important method of administering the drug for systemic effect. Nevertheless, it is probable that at

least 90% of all drugs used to produce systemic effects are administered by the oral route. Patients self-administration cannot be achieved; the sales of the drug constitute only a small fraction of what the market would be otherwise. Drugs that are

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administered orally, solid oral dosage forms represent the preferred class of product. The term oral drug delivery is used to describe the administration of a dosage form orally for local effect or systemic absorption along the gastrointestinal (GI) tract. Oral drug delivery has been the most commonly used route of administration for decades because it is noninvasive, convenient, pain avoidance and has high patient compliance. It does not need any special sterile conditions. The conventional drug delivery systems have been marked with immediate release and frequent dosing of the medication, which could result in the risk of fluctuation in doses hence, there arises a need for formulation with controlled release that is having a nearly constant or equal blood level. Hence, in today's world, most pharmaceutical scientists are engaged in designing an ideal DDS. This system of dealings must be benefited from the advantage of a single dose throughout the period of treatment, and it must administer the drug at a single site in a controlled way. Oral passage of medicament administration for illness is measured as the most conventional route. Tablet is a commonly prescribed dosage form as of its accessibility in terms of self-administration, solidity and simplicity in development. Patients particularly paediatric and geriatric, often experience trouble in swallowing conventional tablets and this problem may prove worst during the traveling conditions due to the non-availability or restricted availability of water. These problems of conventional dosage forms can be encountered by the development of mouth dissolving tablets. These tablets disintegrate in the mouth within a very short span i.e. 20-30 sec and comes in contact with saliva resulting in the therapeutic action of active agent. Mouth dissolving tablets show better patient compliance and acceptance with improved bioavailability, efficacy and biopharmaceutical properties, in contrast to conventional tablets. [1]

2.MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 MATERIALS: -

Cinnarizine was obtained from Rakshit Pharmaceuticals Limited, Microcrystalline cellulose was obtained from Crest Cellulose Private Limited, Cross povidone was obtained from Cradel Pharmaceuticals Private Limited, Talc (Luzenac Pharma) was obtained from Imerys. Magnesium Stearate was obtained from Peter Greven and Mannitol was obtained from Simson Pharma Limited.

2.2 METHODS:

Preformulation Study:

Physical characterization of API sample:

The API sample was observed visually and viewed under microscope for the determination of its nature and then the result were compared with the official book. Then sample was evaluated for its colour, taste and odour. Melting point of Cinnarizine sample was determined by using DSC method. Solubility study was carried out in various media such as 0.1N HCl, pH 6.8 phosphate buffer, Distilled water. Flow of API was determined with the assistance of Bulk density, Tapped density, Carrs' (Compressibility) index, Hausner's ratio, Angle of repose.

Analytical characterization of API Cinnarizine:

Scanning of Cinnarizine in pH buffer 6.8:

10 ug/ml solution of Cinnarizine in pH buffer 6.8 was taken and scanned in range of 400-200 nm against pH buffer 6.8 as a blank using UV spectrophotometer.

Calibration curve of Cinnarizine pH buffer 6.8:

Accurately weighed 100 mg of Cinnarizine and measured 50ml ethanol and transfer into 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolve in suitable quantity of pH buffer 6.8 and lastly make the volume up to 100 ml using pH buffer to obtain a 1000 µg/ml concentration stock solution. About 0.1ml, 0.2 ml, 0.3 ml, 0.4 ml, 0.5 ml of this stock solution (1000 µg/ml) was taken in 100 ml volumetric flask and diluted to 100 ml with pH buffer 6.8 solution to get 1 to 5 µg/ml drug concentration. Then they were analyzed spectrophotometrically by measuring the absorbance at 276 nm. A calibration curve of concentration Vs absorbance was plotted and its intercept and slope value were calculated. [2,3]

Formulation:

Cinnarizine, Crosspovidone, Microcrystalline Cellulose, Magnesium Stearate, Talc, Mannitol and Croscarmellose Sodium were weighed accurately using calibrated weighing balance. Co-shift above ingredient from sieve no. #30. Add above material into blender and blend of 15 minutes. Weight and shift Magnesium Stearate from sieve no. #60. Add shifted material into blender and lubricated for 5 minutes. Then lubricated blend was compressed into tablet using 8.0 mm, round shape, bevel edge, biconvex punches, embossed with “D64” on upper punch and “H” on lower punch.

Table No 1: Formulation trial of batch F01, F02, F03, F04, F05

Sr. NO.	Name of ingredient	F01 (mg/tab)	F02 (mg/tab)	F03 (mg/tab)	F04 (mg/tab)	F05 (mg/tab)
1	Cinnarizine	20	20	20	20	20
2	Cross Povidone	5	10	15	12.5	7.5
3	MCC	162	157	152	154.5	159.5
4	Magnesium Stearate	5	5	5	5	5
5	Talc	5	5	5	5	5
6	Mannitol	1	1	1	1	1
7	Croscarmellose Sodium	2	2	2	2	2
	Total	200	200	200	200	200

Evaluation Studies:

Pre-compression evaluation parameters:

The powder blend of all formulations were evaluated for bulk density, tapped density, carr's index, hausner's ratio and angle of repose to determine its flow properties during compression.

Bulk density:

Apparent bulk density was determined by pouring the powder blend into a measuring cylinder and measuring the volume and weight and bulk density was determine by using formula

$$Db = \frac{M}{Vb}$$

Tapped density:

The pre-weighed powder was filled in measuring cylinder. Then it was tapped in automated bulk density test apparatus. Carry out 10, 500, and 1250 taps on the same powder blend and read the corresponding volumes V10, V500, and V1250. If the difference between V500 and V1250 is less than or equal to 2 ml, V1250 is the final tapped volume. Tapped density was determined by

$$Db = \frac{M}{Vt}$$

Carr's index:

Tapped density (Dt) and bulk density (Db) of powder material was used to measure compressibility of a powder material. It was measure used to describe compression capability of the powder material. Carr's index was determined using following equation

$$\text{Carr's index} = \frac{\text{Dt}-\text{Db}}{\text{Dt}} \times 100$$

Hausner's ratio:

The Hausner's ratio is a number that measures the flowability of a powder material. It is calculated by dividing the tapped density of a material by its bulk density:^[4]

$$\text{HR} = \frac{\text{Dt}}{\text{Db}}$$

Angle of repose:

The angle of repose was determined by using the funnel method. The accurately weight powder blend were taken in the funnel and tip of funnel was blocked by thumb at initially. The height of the funnel was adjusted in such a way the tip of the funnel just touched the apex of the powder blend (Almost 2 cm was fix from plane to tip of funnel). The powder blend was allowed to flow through the funnel freely on to the surface.. It is a measure used to describe flow ability of the powder material. The equation for determining angle of Repose, θ , is ^[5]

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} h/r$$

Post-compression evaluation parameters of finished product:

Weight variation:

The weight of the tablet was measured with the help of digital electronic balance. For determination of weight variation, ten tablets were selected randomly from a batch and average weight was determined^[6].

Thickness:

Ten tablets were selected in a batch for the determination of thickness variation with Vernier Caliper.

Hardness:

Adequate hardness is necessary to withstand the mechanical shock of manufacturing packaging and shipping, and to ensure consumer acceptance. Hardness of tablet was determined using Ewureka hardness tester. The tablet was compressed between a holding ansil and a piston and digital screen showed hardness in kp^[6].

Friability:

Friability of the tablets was determined using an Electrolab friabilator. The tablets should be carefully dedusted before testing. Accurately weigh the tablet sample and place the tablets in the drum. Rotate the drum at 25 rpm for 4 minutes, and remove the tablets. Remove any loose dust from the surface of tablets as before and accurately weigh. Friability was determined by

$$\% \text{ Friability} = \frac{\text{Initial weight}-\text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial Weight}} \times 100$$

Limit: Not more than 1.0%

Drug content:

Five tablets were weighed individually from optimized formulation (F04), then placed in a mortar and powdered with a pestle. An amount equivalent to 100 mg drug was mixed with 100 ml of buffer pH 6.8. The solution was filtered through a Whatmann filter paper (0.22 μm pore size), then diluted with buffer pH 6.8 and then take absorbance at 276 nm wavelength using UV spectrophotometer and the percentage of drug content was calculated by formula^[7]

$$\frac{\text{Drug Content (\%)}}{\frac{\text{Actual Amount of Drug}}{\text{Theoretical Amount of Drug}}} \times 100 = \text{In vitro Disintegration Time :}$$

In-vitro Drug Release Studies:

In-vitro drug release studies of the Cinnarizine finished products were conducted using the USP Apparatus II (rotating paddle method) at a stirring speed of 50 rpm. The dissolution was performed at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ in 900 ml of buffer pH 6.8 solution as the dissolution medium for 24 hours. 2 ml of sample withdrawn at interval of 5,10,15,20,25,30 min with the replacement of equal volume of dissolution media into dissolution flask. Filter the solution through $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ membrane. Dilute the sample with buffer pH 6.8 up to 30 ml into 100 ml volumetric flask. Then samples were analyzed at 276nm by UV spectrophotometer (UV-1800 SHIMADZU)^[8,9]

The disintegration time was performed by apparatus specified in USP at 50 rpm. 900 ml of buffer pH 6.8 was used as disintegration medium and the temperature of $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and time in seconds was taken for complete disintegration of the tablet.

Stability studies of the optimized formulation:

The selected HDPE Bottle packing formulations stored at $40^\circ\text{C}/75\% \text{RH}$ for 1 months and evaluated for their physical appearance and drug release at specified intervals of one month^[10].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Physical characterization of API sample:

Table No. 2: Physical characterization of API Cinnarizine (USP)

Sr. No.	Evaluation Parameters	Method Used	Observed Result
1	Colour	Self-observed	White to cremish
2	State of matter	Optical microscopy	Crystalline
3	Odor	Self-observed	Bitter
4	Taste	Self-observed	Highly Bitter
5	Melting Point	DSC	$118 \pm 122^\circ\text{C}$
6	Residue on ignition	Muffle furnace	0.05 % w/w

Solubility Study:

The solubility of Desvenlafaxine Succinate (USP) in different media is presented in Table No. 4 and

comparison of solubility with in solvent is shown in Figure No. 1.

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Table No. 3: Solubility of Cinnarizine (USP) at 25°C in different media

Sr. No.	Media	Solubility (mg/ml)
1	Purified Water	0.05
2	0.1N HCl	0.30
3	pH 6.8 phosphate buffer	0.15

Figure No. 1: Solubility of Cinnarizine in different media

From table no. 4 it is showing that API have similar solubility in all the studied media store at 25°C.

Derived Properties:

Table No. 4: Bulk density, Tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, Angle of repose of API Desvenlafaxine Succinate

Sr. No	Derived properties	F01	F02	F03	F04	F05
1	Bulk density	0.400gm/ml	0.36gm/ml	0.448gm/ml	0.508gm/ml	0.418
2	Tapped density	0.600 gm/ml	0.450gm/ml	0.49gm/ml	0.667gm/ml	0.472gm/ml
3	Carr's index	33.35	20.00	20.93	33.36	20.11
4	Hausner's ratio	1.5	1.25	1.28	1.52	1.01
5	Angle of repose	57.39°	36.52°	41.76°	57.79°	40.80°

From Table no. 4, it is shown that API has poor flow.

Analytical characterization of API Cinnarizine:

Scanning of Cinnarizine in buffer pH 6.8:

Figure No. 2: UV spectra of Cinnarizine in buffer pH 6.8 at 276 nm

From figure no. 2 it is found that maximum absorbance of Cinnarizine was at the wavelength 276 nm.

Calibration curve of Cinnarizine buffer pH 6.8:

A spectrophotometric method for estimation of Cinnarizine, based on the measurement of absorbance at 276 nm in buffer pH 6.8, gives a straight line with an equation: $y = 0.2888x + 0.0157$ and $r^2 = 0.9988$ (Figure 3).

Figure No. 3: Standard calibration curve of Cinnarizine in buffer pH 6.8 at 276nm

Drug–excipient compatibility study by using FTIR spectroscopy-

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Figure No. 4: FTIR spectrum of pure API Cinnarizine

Table No. 5: Functional group and principle peaks present in Cinnarizine

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group	Type of Vibration	Assignment
3901–3747	O–H, N–H	Stretching (broad)	Moisture or amine/hydroxyl groups
3500.80	N–H / O–H	Stretching	Hydrogen-bonded O–H or N–H
3022–2806	C–H (aromatic & aliphatic)	Stretching	Aromatic and alkyl groups
2682–2340	Possibly overtones	Combination / overtone bands	Possible impurities or CO ₂ environment
2158–1957	C≡C or C≡N (if present)	Stretching	Less common, trace peaks
1896–1649	C=O, C=N	Stretching	Imine or aromatic ketone (C=N or C=O groups)
1587–1448	C=C (aromatic), N–H	Stretching / bending	Aromatic ring or amine group
1371–1278	C–H bending	Bending	Aliphatic side chains
1139–1001	C–N, C–O	Stretching	Amines, ethers, esters
932–707	Aromatic ring bending	Bending / deformation	Out-of-plane C–H bending
615–476	Skeletal vibrations	Bending	Backbone deformation

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Figure No. 5: FTIR spectrum of API Crosscarmellose Sodium

Table No.6: Functional group and principle peaks present in Croscarmellose Sodium

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group	Type of Vibration	Assignment
3901–3446	O–H (Hydroxyl), N–H	Stretching (broad)	Moisture, hydroxyl groups in cellulose
3122–2891	C–H (Aliphatic)	Stretching	Methylene and methyl groups in polymer backbone
2343–2056	CO ₂ / trace gases	Combination bands / overtone	Atmospheric artifact
1942–1649	C=O, COO ⁻ (Carboxylate)	Stretching (asymmetric)	Carboxylate salt groups (sodium carboxymethyl)
1541	N–H, COO ⁻	Bending	Carboxylate / amide group presence
1417–1340	C–H, COO ⁻	Bending / symmetric stretching	Aliphatic CH or carboxylate ions
1201–1078	C–O, C–O–C	Stretching	Ether/ester bonds in cellulose backbone
931–707	C–O–C, Ring vibrations	Bending / deformation	Polysaccharide ring structure
576–437	Skeletal vibrations	Deformation	Backbone vibrations, less specific

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Figure No. 6: FTIR spectrum of API Cinnarazine and Croscarmellose Sodium

Table No. 7: Functional group and principle peaks present in physical mixture of API mixture of Cinnarizine and Croscarmellose Sodium

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group	Type of Vibration	Assignment
3901–3747	O–H, N–H	Broad stretching	Hydrogen bonding, moisture
3562–2806	C–H (aliphatic)	Stretching	Alkyl chains from both cinnarizine and polymer
2698–2343	CO ₂ / overtones	Possibly combination bands	Environmental / trace signals
2253–1896	C≡C, C=N or C=O	Stretching	Imine or conjugated carbonyl
1741–1541	C=O, COO ⁻	Stretching	Carboxylate and amide functionalities
1448–1278	CH ₂ , CH ₃	Bending	Aliphatic side chains and polysaccharide signals
1139–1001	C–O, C–N	Stretching	Ester, ether, and amine linkages
923–707	Aromatic or carbohydrate ring	Out-of-plane bending	Polysaccharide or aromatic C–H
615–430	Skeletal vibrations	Deformation	Polymer and drug matrix framework

From table no 5,6 and 7, FTIR spectral analysis of pure Cinnarizine, pure Croscarmellose Sodium and its mixture of drug and polymer(Cinnarizine and Croscarmellose Sodium),no significant peak shifts, new interactions, or degradation products were observed. Thus, Cinnarizine is compatible with the selected excipients based on FTIR analysis, confirming its stability in the proposed formulation.

Evaluation Studies:

Pre-compression evaluation parameters:

From table no. 8 The evaluated powder blends (F01–F05) demonstrated varying flow properties based on their angle of repose, compressibility index, and Hausner's ratio.

Table No. 8: Pre-compression evaluation parameters of the powder blend

Formulation code	Bulk density (g/ml)	Tapped density (g/ml)	Compressibility index	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose (degree)
F01	0.344	0.439	19.56	1.26	36.52
F02	0.448	0.545	17.79	1.21	38.88
F03	0.383	0.460	16.73	1.20	39.80
F04	0.508	0.667	23.83	1.31	41.73
F05	0.437	0.538	18.77	1.23	37.99

Post-compression evaluation parameters of Physical parameters of batch from F01 to F05: finished product:

Table No. 9: Physical parameters of batch from F01 to F05

Sr. No.	Parameters	F01	F02	F03	F04	F05
1	Average weight (mg)	190.6-200.8	196.6-200.7	197.3-200.6	196.1-210.5	198.9-204.5
2	Thickness (mm)	4.69-4.73	4.59-4.65	4.59-4.64	4.71-4.75	3.0-3.4
3	Hardness (kp)	8.4-8.10	8.0-8.6	8.0-8.6	8.6-9.2	8.5-8.9
4	Friability %	0.59	0.69	0.14	0.88	0.70
	In vitro disintegration time	11.5	13.0	16.5	18.9	18.0

DISCUSSION:

Batches F01, F02, F03, F04 and F05 were evaluated. The tablets exhibited consistent average weights ranging from **190.6 to 210.5 mg**, with uniform thickness between **3.00 mm and 4.75 mm**, reflecting controlled compression and uniformity in tablet size. Tablet hardness values ranged from **8.0 to 9.2 kp**, indicating sufficient

mechanical strength for further processing. Friability for all batches remained well within the acceptable pharmacopeial limit of less than 1%, with **F03** showing the lowest friability at **0.14%**, indicating comparatively better tablet robustness.

In-vitro drug release profile of batch F01, F02, F03, F04 and F05

Table No. 10: In-vitro drug release profile of batch F01, F02, F03, F04 and F05 in release media buffer pH 6.8

Time (MIN)	F01	F02	F03	F04	F05
0	0	0	0	0	0
5	20.46 ±0.4	20.46±0.1	20.03±0.1	25.01±0.4	30.00±0.1
10	40.10±0.4	40.25±0.2	50.17±0.2	50.00±0.2	60.04 ±0.2
15	50.07±0.6	51.08±0.5	60.71±0.1	64.10±0.1	70.09±0.5
20	65.03±0.4	69.08±0.3	71.95±0.5	74.02±0.3	80.01±0.6
25	74.07±0.2	68.33±0.6	74.02±0.2	80.01±0.4	86.01 ±0.4
30	80.14 ±0.4	75.05±0.1	79.01±0.6	93.01±0.3	88.01 ±0.3

Figure No. 7: In-vitro drug release profile of batch F01, F02,F03,F04 and F05 in release media buffer pH 6.8

DISCUSSION:

In batch F01, poor flow properties of the lubricated blend resulted in weight variation and inconsistent drug release, with a final release of 74.07%. F02 showed slightly improved flow but exhibited a faster drug release, with a final release of 75.05%. F03 achieved better control with 79.01%. Overall, all three batches released the drug too quickly, indicating insufficient polymer concentration to sustain release. These results prompted an increase in polymer content in further formulations to achieve better control profile. All tablet parameters were within acceptable limits,

and the flow properties of the lubricated blends were improved due to increased lubricant concentration. Batch F04, formulated with a 1:1.75 drug-to-polymer ratio, showed a drug release of 93.01%. Hence, F04 was selected as the optimized batch.

Stability Studies of optimized formulation:

Stability studies were carried out at 40°C/75% RH for optimized formulation (F04) for 1 month. After each month physical changes like colour, drug content and dissolution profile were recorded.

Table No. 11: Stability study data of optimized formulation (F04) at 40°C/75% RH for 1 month

Formulation F04	Initial	1M 40°C/75% RH HDPE Bottle
(1) Physical stability	White, round shaped	Similar to initial
(2) Drug content (%)	99.28 %	98.76 %
(3) Dissolution Parameters	Apparatus type:USP-II, rpm:-50, Media:-buffer pH6.8 in water, Media volume:-900ml, Sampling points:-5,10,15,20,25,30 min.	
Time in min	Cumulative percent drug release	Cumulative percent drug release
5	25.01±0.4	17.64±0.6
10	50.00±0.2	25.15±0.7
15	64.10±0.1	45.32±0.9
20	74.02±0.3	65.09±0.5
25	80.01±0.4	81.70±0.6
30	93.01±0.3	90.00±1.2
Conclusion	24 Hrs profile	Similar to initial

DISCUSSION-

Table No.22 shows the stability performance of formulation **F04** stored at **40°C/75% RH for 1 months**. Initially, **physical appearance** remained consistent throughout the study. The tablets retained their original **white , round-shaped form** at all checkpoints (1 months), indicating that the elevated temperature and humidity had no adverse effect on the physical integrity or external features of the dosage form. The drug content was **99.28%**, which slightly decreased to **97.58%** by the one month, remaining within acceptable limits. The initial drug release at 24 hours was **93.01%**, compared to **90.00%**, at 1month. A slight increase in early time-point release was observed post-storage, likely due to minor changes in polymer behavior under high temperature and humidity. However, the overall drug release profile remained similar to the initial. These results confirm that **F04** maintains its physical stability, drug content and extended-release characteristics under accelerated conditions, supporting its robustness for long-term storage.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

The present research focused on the formulation and in vitro evaluation of Mouth dissolving tablet of Cinnarazine for the treatment of vertigo, nausea, vomiting, and motion sickness. In the present study an attempt was made to formulate directly compressible orally disintegrating tablets of cinnarazine with an objective to assist patients of any age group for easy administration. A total of five formulations (F01–F05) were developed using varying concentrations of polymers such as croscarmellose sodium. Microcrystalline cellulose was used as a disintegrants. The drug-excipient compatibility studies confirmed no significant interactions, ensuring the stability of the formulation. The formulations **F01-F03** Contained croscarmellose sodium at increasing

concentrations. F03 showed rapid drug release, necessitating an increase in polymer concentration in later formulations. **F04-F05** show exhibited an optimal drug release profile. Among all the developed formulations, batch F04 was identified as the optimized formulation based on its pre-compression and post-compression evaluation parameters. The key factors contributing to its optimization include: **Physical and Mechanical Properties:** F04 demonstrated excellent hardness, friability, weight variation, in vitro disintegration time and meeting pharmacopoeial standards. **Stability Studies:** The stability studies conducted at 40°C/75% RH for one months confirmed that batch F04 retained its physical characteristics, drug content and drug release profile, ensuring long-term formulation stability. The formulated mouth dissolving tablet of Cinnarazine (F04) was successfully developed and evaluated, FTIR studies concluded that drug and excipients were compatible with each other. The formulated tablets were satisfactory in terms of hardness, thickness, friability, weight variation, drug content, , in vitro disintegration time and in vitro drug release. **Hence, the optimized formulation of MDT (F04) can serve as a promising alternative for the effective management of life threatening disease.**

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